

*Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology
Systems (FOWTs)*

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The MARINEWIND project aims to pinpoint challenges and potential opportunities for enhancing the role of floating offshore wind technology in innovative system integration solutions. The project will explore market dynamics, policy and regulatory issues, social considerations, financial aspects, techno-economic solutions, and recommendations for storage and flexibility provisions.

This report presents the outcomes of the initial co-creation workshop in the UK, where stakeholders from diverse backgrounds in the wind sector gathered to identify and clarify their needs. Insights were collected from more than sixty industry professionals through workshop discussions and interviews. These insights will be instrumental in analysing barriers and facilitators related to the region's social, environmental, technological, and financial aspects.

The analysis will be integrated into the MARINEWIND web-based Geographical Information System (webGIS), which will provide tailored information on Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWT) to stakeholders based on their category, location, and objectives. The system will also offer policy recommendations for informed Renewable Energy Sources (RES) policies and strategies to enhance societal acceptance (WP4). The Replicability Plan will facilitate the transfer of knowledge.

In the ongoing MARINEWIND project, efforts will focus on transferring knowledge from established experiences to potential floating offshore sites in various planning or implementation stages, especially in Scotland, Wales, and England. This will lead to developing short-term and long-term strategies to expedite the deployment and commercialisation of floating offshore wind technology in the region.

Key stakeholders agreed on the primary obstacles to floating wind deployment. Collaborative efforts and knowledge sharing were crucial factors in accelerating floating wind technology's learning curve and deployment. This includes upgrades in port infrastructure, coordinated grid designs, and providing investment certainty to foster supply chain growth.

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: Floating Wind 2023, P&J Live, Aberdeen

EVENT DATE: 5th October 2023 14:30-16:00

EVENT TITLE: Side Event- Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Co-creation Workshop

EVENT AFFILIATION: European Maritime Day (EMD) 2023

LEAD ORGANISER: Energy Systems Catapult

LANGUAGE: English

CONCEPT: The workshop aims to bring together industry leaders, experts, and stakeholders to discuss and explore effective market measures for the rapid expansion of floating offshore wind projects in the UK.

Under the theme “*Market Uptake Measures to Boost Floating Wind*,” the event highlighted how local authorities and industry collaborate to help the floating wind sector move faster and more safely towards commercial deployment.

OBJECTIVES

The workshop’s specific objectives were to enable industry engagement to explore. Innovative market strategies to accelerate the deployment of floating offshore wind in UK waters.

Specifically, delving into collective industry insights and identifying key enablers that can drive progress in crucial areas of offshore wind technology.

- Gain deep insights into market strategies for floating offshore wind deployment.
- Collaborate with industry experts and peers.
- Contribute to meaningful discussions that can drive progress in the offshore wind sector.

MARINEWIND objectives:

- Increase awareness of FOWTs via co-creation activities that directly engage policy and decision makers, market and business actors, civil society organisations and funding bodies.
- Encourage social acceptance by directly involving local communities and fishers and addressing environmental issues.
- Facilitate communication and collaboration among all the stakeholders directly and indirectly involved in Italian MARINEWIND Lab

TARGET AUDIENCE

The event targeted representatives of public authorities, supply chains, investors (public/private), standardisation and certification bodies, research institutes and industry involved in the floating offshore wind sector. For each specific category, the involved actors were:

- Industry: Technology and project developers,
- Supply chain: Port infrastructure, cable design and installation, OEM companies, tech/project developers, and trade associations (fisheries and tourism).
- Research institutes: Scientific & Research Community.
- Public authorities: at European (EC, European associations, e.g., ICLEI, ERRIN), national (Ministries for Energy, for Industry and Environment) and local level (Regional authorities), maritime transport authorities, policymakers.
- Civil society: NGOs, civil society organisations, and citizens.
- Green innovation: SMEs, public/private financial investors, insurers, ecologists, environmental organisations, and natural parks.

The event also targeted actors and beneficiaries of other EU and UK funded projects and initiatives through dissemination activities and synergies.

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT:

Thirty-three participants were initially registered for the event. Fourteen attended the workshop, while eighteen others were interviewed both before and after the event due to their inability to attend in person.

Stakeholder group	Organisations	Attendees/ Interviewees
Supply chain	Port of Aberdeen	Attendee (1)
	COWI (JDR cables)	Attendee (2)
	Global Energy Group (Port of Nigg)	Interviewed (1)
Technology/Project Developers	Corio Generation	Interviewed (1)
	SSE Renewables	Interviewed (2)
	Simply Blue	Interviewed (1)
Funding/Investors	SENER	Attendee (1)
	Wave Energy Scotland	Interviewee (1) Attendee (1)
Public Authority	The Crown Estate	Attendee (1)
	Scottish Government	Attendee (1) Interviewee (2)
Consultancy services	APRE	Attendee (1)
	WavEC Renewables	Attendee (1)
	Carbon Trust	Attendee (1) Interviewee (1)
Research Organisation	Offshore Renewables Catapult	Interviewee (4)

Academia	Energy Systems Catapult	Attendee (3) Interviewee (3)
	University of York	Attendee (1)
	University of Edinburgh	Interviewee (2)

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

It was a positive experience at the Floating Offshore Wind conference in Aberdeen, where industry experts gathered to discuss challenges and opportunities in the offshore wind sector. The conference revealed a cautious industry outlook, focusing on technical challenges, especially in floating offshore wind. There is a need for the sector to adjust expectations regarding the deployment of floating offshore wind in Scotland and address market challenges such as commodity pricing and capital costs.

The discussions during the workshop and the conference highlighted thoughts on innovative technologies like floating Offshore Wind and tidal streams, emphasising the importance of tailored support and careful management of the Contract for Difference (CfD) mechanisms. The speakers expressed optimism about the industry’s future despite a temporary slowdown in the UK, seeing it as an opportunity for consolidation and focusing on established leases.

The keynote speakers and panellists also shared insights from discussions on environmental impact assessments and emerging topics like high voltage dynamic cables and digitalisation in the operational phase of offshore wind projects. They all emphasised the industry’s innovative spirit and commitment to progress.

Scotland is a world leader in the deployment of floating wind and currently has the two world’s largest operational floating wind farms, with a third under development, which will supersede these two wind farms to become the world’s largest project. The announcement of the winning projects in the ScotWind leasing round on 17 January 2022 has added just over 26.5GW of commercial scale floating wind spread across 17 projects. The additional Clearing Round, announced on 22 August 2022, has added three more projects totalling 2.8GW. Adding additional developer capacity to ScotWind has raised the final round total to just over 30GW.

Figure 1- Offshore Wind Farms in Scotland¹

¹ <https://www.offshorewindscotland.org.uk/the-offshore-wind-market-in-scotland/>

3 ROUNDTABLES TOPICS OVERVIEW

3.1 Keynote The Crown Estate

Tim Stiven, Senior Development Manager (Marine), the Crown Estate:

- **Arrangements for Leasing Rounds (AR5) & Critical Challenges:** Focus on the latest leasing round arrangements (AR5); for instance, there is a requirement to address crucial issues like project development areas (pre-surveying work), buffer and exclusion zones, Holistic Network design pathways with grid matching design with ESCO's reduced time for spatial design and planning (18 months), and the preparedness and early commitments to port infrastructure investment and development.
- **Supportive Investment Funding:** The need for funding options that complement investments in offshore projects.
- **Supply Chain Capacity:** Assess the capacity and robustness of the supply chain supporting offshore operations.
- **Market De-risking Strategies:** Implement measures to reduce risks associated with the offshore market and fit-for-purpose policies to help shape the industry.

Some enabling factors:

- **Habitats Regulations Assessment (HRA) before Seabed Lease:** Conduct an HRA prior to seabed leasing to understand sea characteristics before selecting sites.
- **Grid Design Optimisation:** Align grid design with ESO's shortened spatial design and planning timeline (18 months).
- **Pre-Surveying Initiatives:** Undertake pre-surveying work to gather essential data and insights before project initiation.
- **Enhancing Supply Chain: by ensuring** early commitment to port infrastructure investment and deployments, engaging communities by emphasising social value aspects such as skills development, equality, diversity, and enhancing nature.
- **Addressing seabed rights** to establish a secure foundation for offshore projects.

3.2 Keynote SuperGEN ORE

Prof Deborah Greaves OBE, SuperGEN ORE

- **Promoting Technological Advancements and Research:** Investing in research and development is key to encouraging innovation within the supply chain. This investment drives the creation of advanced materials, manufacturing methods, and components.
- **Flexibility and Co-location Advantages:** Recognising the benefits of flexibility and co-location in enhancing operational efficiency and collaboration within the industry. Considering co-location aspects and landscape factors in the planning and development process.

- **Strengthening the Supply Chain:** Establishing a competitive supply chain to effectively meet industry demands, focusing on local content development and workforce training initiatives to fortify the supply chain.
- **Overcoming challenges related to consenting Processes** through research and development, data capture and sharing to accelerate the consenting process.
- **SuperGEN's Role in Research Advancement:** Acknowledging SuperGEN's contribution to advancing research through flexible funding calls and other priority initiatives, bridging the gap known as the Valley of Death in research and development.

3.3 Theme- Role of Electricity Networks, Flexibility & Co-location

In this session, we discussed the role of electricity networks and flexibility in the context of floating offshore wind and the benefits of co-location opportunities for floating offshore wind, delving into areas like operational efficiencies and technological innovations required for successful co-location projects.

3.3.1 Dr Corentin Jankowiak, Network and Storage Systems Engineer at Energy Systems Catapult

Corentin discussed the influence of floating offshore wind technologies on the demand for flexibility and how flexibility can aid in integrating floating offshore wind. Various potential technologies were also discussed that can provide flexibility to support floating offshore wind and the necessary factors (flexibility enablers) essential for implementing these flexibility solutions. Some of the specific points addressed were:

- **Multi-Vector Energy Challenge:** Addressing the complex challenge of managing multiple energy vectors and their interconnections in the context of floating offshore wind technologies.
- **Imbalanced generation:** Analysing the issue of generation imbalances and how flexibility solutions can help stabilise the energy grid, especially concerning floating offshore wind energy production.
- **Role of Transmission Control & Storage:** Delving into the pivotal roles of transmission control systems and energy storage solutions in maintaining grid stability and ensuring efficient energy flow from floating offshore wind farms.
- **Demand Side Response (DSR) Aspects (V2G, etc.):** Exploring Demand Side Response (DSR) strategies such as Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology and other aspects that contribute to balancing energy demand and supply, particularly in the context of floating offshore wind integration.

3.3.2 Francisco Correia da Fonseca, Head of Engineering & Operations, WavEC Offshore Renewables

1. Key areas in need of innovation to advance the floating wind sector:
 - a. Improved collaboration in demonstrating high potential innovative technologies: High potential technologies such as quick connectors and innovative crane concepts that climb onto the tower or nacelle and enhance the assembly of the WTG on the FOW and/or large component replacements. However, there is a catch-22

paradoxical situation going on. OEMs and FOW project developers wait for innovative technologies to be demonstrated and validated before adopting them. However, technology developers need the support and collaboration of OEMs to demonstrate and validate their innovations. Each party is waiting for the other to make the first move, leading to a standstill in technological advancement.

- b. Collaborative innovation through joint ventures, innovation clusters, funding and financing is fundamental.
 - c. Improving the use of space, namely through hybridisation of offshore renewables or multi-use
2. Discussed primary challenges associated with aligning the needs of floating wind projects with port requirements- There needs to be a timing mismatch between the port upgrades and the floating offshore wind projects. In the case of Portugal, while the floating wind projects are slated for installation by 2030, the port upgrades, essential for supporting these projects, take about 4-5 years to complete. However, project developers are only willing to invest in port upgrades once they have the certainty of winning the auction, the results of which will be out in 2025. Given the installation timelines, there is a clear scheduling conflict, as the ports may need more time to be ready to support the wind projects if we wait for floating wind developers to take the initiative.

3.3.3 Tim Hurst, Managing Director of Wave Energy Scotland (WES)

- Key notes on opportunities for floating offshore wind to be integrated into hybrid energy systems, combining wind power with other renewable sources. Tim gave an example of wave energy as the study WES recently completed, looking to investigate the potential of combined wind/wave structures².
- Key findings highlighting systems benefits of integrating wave energy to floating wind, including cost benefits, co-development, and sharing of supply chains between wind and wave energy, making a strong contribution to the local content of a floating wind project.
- 500 MW exploitable wave resource between turbines (1 km distance), peak wave generation follows peak wind generation by four days.
- Cost savings from 40% to 70% for wave farms when collocated with wind farms.
- Reluctance from the wind sector and need for in-depth analysis of seabed for multi-functionality.

3.4 Theme- Policy & Regulation

Addressing policy and regulatory challenges for floating offshore wind requires a collaborative effort between governments, regulatory bodies, industry stakeholders, and environmental experts. This session explored the required robust policies and regulations tailored to floating offshore wind and the

² <https://www.waveenergyscotland.co.uk/media/1471/o-lo-r10-031956-r02-final-report.pdf>

government's role in promoting a sustainable, innovative, and environmentally responsible energy future.

3.4.1 David Wilson, Senior Project Manager on the OSSIAN project, SSE renewables

In absentia, David shared challenges faced by the floating offshore wind projects and other renewable technologies, such as commodity prices, inflation, consenting, and grid timescales, and the unique challenges associated with current high price points and market uncertainty, with uncertainty contributing to high-cost estimates.

Role of Long-term Governmental Policy:

1. **Long term and consistent governmental policy** are a key enabler to improving certainty and to realising the ambitions of the floating offshore wind industry. This is true for several core topics (outline three key ones):
 - CfD mechanism (retain the separate pot for floating wind, be clear and aligned on the definition of floating technology and consider phased CfD for floating as is the case for fixed projects).
 - Support investment in infrastructure, particularly UK ports (i.e., FLOWMIS and Green Freeports). Ports require considerable levels of investment to be able to be used by projects. Investors need confidence in the floating offshore wind market that projects will be developed and constructed and the timeline. Projects alone cannot provide ports with sufficient confidence in the required timeframe to be ready to receive orders / have the necessary facilities constructed (mismatch between investment timing and project developer milestone certainty; consent, CfD, FID).
2. **Three Core Topics:**
 - CfD Mechanism: Clear definition and separate pot for floating wind; phased CfD for floating projects similar to fixed projects.
 - Investment in Infrastructure: Support for port infrastructure investment, essential for project development; mismatch between investment timing and project milestones.
 - Grid System Fit for the Future: Focus on creating a grid system fit for the 2030s and beyond; policy changes and investment in electrical infrastructure are needed.
 1. Floating offshore wind is a novel industry that faces many challenges, some of which it shares with other renewable generation technologies (commodity prices, inflation, consenting and grid timescales) and others more unique to floating wind.
 2. Two key challenges: Current price point and market uncertainty. Uncertainty is at least part of the cause of the current high price point estimations.

3. Grid system fit for the 2030s and beyond If governmental targets for floating offshore wind and renewable generation, in general, are to be met. Considerable focus must be placed upon realising a grid system fit for the 2030s and beyond. Not only does this require a huge investment in electrical infrastructure, but it also requires significant policy changes to allow the new vision of a holistic and coordinated network design to work. The highly varied connection regime (radial, offshore non-radial, transmission operator, interconnector) can create an uneven playing field between projects if the right policies are not implemented. This will take time to happen, and yet developers need certainty in this regard soon to be able to order long lead electrical infrastructure items at a suitable time.

In summary, policies around floating offshore wind must support the long-term certainty of the floating offshore wind industry. This will allow ScotWind projects to be at the forefront of commercial scale floating offshore wind, getting us closer to net zero, bringing benefits to our energy security, and enabling a local supply chain and a grid system fit for the coming decades.

3.5 Theme- Supply Chain Challenges

This session focussed on a comprehensive discussion of the challenges faced by the supply chain for floating offshore wind by sharing their insights and proposing enablers for a sustainable and competitive industry, as well as addressing the requirements and challenges related to ports and infrastructure for successfully developing floating offshore wind projects. There are complex facets, including technical requirements, logistical challenges, environmental impact assessments, and investor buy-in.

3.5.1 Aldara Martinez, Offshore Wind team, SENER

Aldara discussed measures that can be taken to achieve economies of scale within the supply chain, driving down costs and making floating offshore wind more competitive with other forms of renewable energy. These points address the focus on driving down costs, enhancing competitiveness, and broadening the perspective beyond technological aspects to include socio-economic and environmental considerations in the context of floating offshore wind energy.

1. **Achieving Economies of Scale in Supply Chain:** Aldara discussed measures to achieve economies of scale within the supply chain to drive down costs and enhance the competitiveness of floating offshore wind compared to other renewable energy sources. Reduce saturation of the supply by standardisation
2. **Role of the Value Chain in Floating Offshore Wind Development:** the value chain can support the development and acceptance of floating offshore wind, emphasising the need to foster contributions beyond technological feasibility, indicating a broader perspective. Considering socio-economic and environmental factors was also highlighted as key to supporting the value chain.

3.5.2 Mary Harvey, Senior Associate at the Carbon Trust *Carbon Trust*.

Mary discussed challenges facing the supply chain with increased pressures to meet non-price criteria. Supply chain challenges are exaggerated through the pressure of NPC. While NPC is important and needed to help shape the industry, it speaks about the supply chain's difficulties:

- **Increased Pressures:** The supply chain faces challenges due to increased pressures to meet non-price criteria (NPC).
- **Exaggeration of Challenges:** These challenges are exacerbated by the pressure of NPC requirements, highlighting the supply chain's difficulties.
- **Importance of NPC:** NPC is important for shaping the industry but poses significant challenges to the supply chain.
- **Sustainability Challenges:** Sustainability challenges intensify pressure on the already stressed supply chain.

3.5.3 Marlene Mitchell, Commercial Manager Port of Aberdeen

Marlene addressed requirements and challenges related to ports and infrastructure, which are vital for successfully developing floating offshore wind projects. These are complex facets, including technical requirements, logistical challenges, environmental impact assessments, and investor buy-in.

Marlene also touched on key considerations and challenges in planning and constructing ports to support floating wind turbines' assembly, deployment, and maintenance. Characteristics such as water depth, size and footprint required design draft needed, the height of wind turbines, restrictions such as air restrictions (CAA), stability requirements, transport, weight, cost of hire, need for wet storage, etc.

1. Considerations and Challenges in Planning and Constructing Ports:

- **Water Depth, Size, and Footprint:** Considerations include characteristics such as water depth, size, and footprint required for port design.
- **Design Draft:** Planning must consider the necessary design draft for ports.
- **Wind Turbine Height:** Ports must accommodate the height of wind turbines.
- **Regulatory Restrictions:** Consideration of regulatory restrictions, such as air restrictions imposed by the Civil Aviation Authority (CAA).
- **Stability Requirements:** Ensuring stability of infrastructure in various conditions.
- **Transport and Weight Considerations:** Addressing challenges related to transport and weight of components.
- **Cost of Hire:** Factoring in the cost of hiring necessary equipment.
- **Need for Wet Storage:** Assessing the need for wet storage facilities.

2. Key Considerations and Challenges:

- **Integration into Early Planning:** Port infrastructure needs to be integrated into the early planning stages of offshore wind projects.
- **Understanding Risk Models:** Understanding risk models related to port and infrastructure development.
- **Supply Chain Management:** Key storage for the supply chain, for example, JDR, needs to be considered.
- **Manufacturing Plans:** Planning around manufacturing processes and their integration with port activities.
- **Local Content:** Considering the incorporation of local content and resources.
- **Traffic Management:** Managing traffic flow and coordination around the port area.
- **Lack of standardisation**
- Financial risk taken by ports to conduct work before contacts have been finalised.

3.6 Theme- Licensing and Consenting Challenges

We all know that addressing the challenges of licensing and consenting for floating offshore wind is crucial for understanding the regulatory complexities of this industry. The session discussed the intricacies of navigating the regulatory landscape for floating offshore wind, highlighting the unique challenges and opportunities it presents.

3.6.1 Debbie England, Marine Directorate for Licensing & Consenting, Scottish Government

Debbie provided an overview of the licensing and consenting challenges and the associated considerations for floating offshore wind projects:

1. Licensing and Consenting Processes for Floating Offshore Wind Projects:

- **Complex Regulatory Frameworks:** Debbie discussed the challenges posed by complex regulatory frameworks in the licensing and consenting processes for floating offshore wind projects.
- **Environmental Considerations:** The importance of considering environmental factors during these processes, including habitats, anchors, and other sea users.

2. Challenges faced by Developers:

- **Data Sharing:** Developers face challenges related to data sharing, indicating the importance of access to relevant and accurate information.
- **Monitoring:** Highlighted the need to continuously monitor offshore wind projects to ensure compliance with regulations and environmental standards.
- **Involvement of Nature Scotland and Regulatory Bodies in Scottish Renewables:** Mentioned the involvement of regulatory bodies, such as Nature Scotland, in the context of Scottish renewables projects.
- **Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) for Habitats, Anchors, and Other Sea Users:** Developers encounter challenges conducting thorough EIAs for habitats, anchors, and other sea users, reflecting the complexity of environmental considerations.

3.7 Theme- Financing and Economic Barriers

3.7.1 Dr Paola Zerilli, Associate Professor in Finance, University of York

Paola provided an overview of the UK industry's challenges, focus areas, and the specific challenges related to the floating offshore wind sector, from financial strategies, collaborative efforts needed to secure investments, and cost reduction feasibility.

1. **Challenges in the UK Industry Post-CfD Results:** Paola mentioned challenges in financing and economic viability post-CfD (Contracts for Difference) results in the wind sector, highlighting financial viability measures to be considered despite the economic challenges.
2. **Challenges in the Floating Offshore Wind Sector:** Discussed financial strategies in the floating offshore wind sector, the collaboration efforts needed to secure investments, and the feasibility of reducing costs in the floating offshore wind sector.
3. **Key Areas of Focus for Addressing Challenges:**

- **Green Rustic Procurement:** Related to environmentally friendly sourcing or procurement practices.
- **Collaboration:** Stressing the importance of collaboration among stakeholders.
- **Better Forecasting:** Emphasising the need for improved predictions or projections.
- **Agile Approach to Changes:** Advocating for flexibility and adaptability in dealing with industry changes.
- **Better Modelling and understanding of Bounds and Risks:** Highlighting the importance of accurate modelling and risk assessment.
- **Consideration of Factors such as Pricing, Contracts for Difference (CFD), Material, and Return on Investment (ROI):** Indicating the complexity of factors that need to be considered for decision-making in the wind sector.

3.8 Theme- CR&D

3.8.1 Ralph Torr, OREC

Globally, at European and UK levels, challenges in the floating offshore wind sector persist in the short term (by 2030) and the medium-to-long term (2035-2055). Addressing these challenges is urgent, with varying degrees of immediacy. Ralph discussed the urgency in mitigating the following barriers to advance the sector:

- **Technical complexity:** The intricate nature of floating aspects, incorporating multiple components such as foundations, anchors, and cables, necessitates a clear and straightforward engineering interface. Challenges encompass turbine, sub-structure, mooring systems, and commercial interfaces.
- **Design Optimisation and Data Sharing:** Although designing mooring and anchoring systems is not inherently difficult, optimising these designs requires efficient feedback loops and data-sharing mechanisms. Existing designs can be enhanced through a commercial interface, but challenges arise in sharing this information effectively.
- **Cost Pressures** to support artificial learning demand. In this case, Research, Development, and Innovation (RD&I) funding is crucial to support learning. However, this funding is discretionary, and uncertainties persist regarding grant allocations and testing demonstrated in the UK.
- **Supply Chain Complexity:** It is well known that intense global competition for key components affects costs and risks. Coordinating wind turbine and substructure manufacturing requires a **systematic approach**, with challenges extending to port infrastructure and grid reinforcement.
- **Grid Reinforcement and Policy Uncertainty:** the delivery plan for net zero, coupled with a lack of forward guidance, impacts grid infrastructure. Clear government policies regarding the grid, pricing, and distribution are essential. Additionally, leasing rounds and grid connections require coordinated efforts and clarity.

- **Leasing Area Challenges:** clarity is lacking in additional leasing areas and the necessary financial support. A **coordinated effort** is needed to meet ambitious targets set by regulatory bodies. In addition, sharing of lessons learned into a lease agreement and public support (CfD)-mandating sharing as regulatory. Incentivising or rewarding innovation- mandating share of lessons learnt or knowledge of deployment to accelerate innovation pathway in Fixed/Floating Wind projects. An example is the Kincardine Floating Offshore Wind farm (Lessons Learned are not shareable, or there are no requirements to share lessons learnt), leading to deliver value, with extremely limited (to none) data sharing on lessons learned.
- **Training, Skills, and Regulatory Complexities:** Lack of clarity in regulatory processes delays progress. Challenges persist in developing and consenting processes, requiring streamlined regulatory authority, training, skills development, and a robust supply chain.
- Addressing these challenges means **Data Sharing and Feedback Mechanisms:** Implementing efficient data sharing mechanisms and **feedback loops** is critical for optimising designs and enhancing efficiency.
- **Policy Clarity and Investment Confidence:** Clear, long-term government policies, especially concerning **grid infrastructure and pricing**, are imperative. Providing investment confidence through transparent policies is vital for attracting investors and fostering sector growth.
- **Systematic Coordination:** Coordinated manufacturing and supply chain management efforts are essential. Developing a systematic approach for attracting investments, including **addressing port infrastructure and grid reinforcement**, is crucial.
- **Incentives and Long-term Management:** Incentivising innovation and providing long-term guidance, particularly in areas guaranteed by Marine Spatial Planning, is necessary to foster a stable, long-term view for investors and the supply chain. In addition,
- **Addressing Regulatory Complexity:** Simplifying regulatory processes and providing a clear plan to support ambitious targets set by regulatory authorities are essential for credible and achievable outcomes. Coordinated efforts are required to facilitate the physical realisation of targets, aligning with capabilities and market realities.

3.8.2 Charmalee Jayamaha, Beth Warnock, Romina Arefin, Power Systems Engineers, ESC

Key challenges highlighted by the power systems team at Energy Systems Catapult were linked to **grid Investment Challenges:** Under-investment in the grid will lead to slower adoption of renewables and higher fossil fuel use. According to the latest IEA report³ and the Electricity Networks Commissioner's report⁴, Cumulative CO₂ emissions in the Grid Delay Case are 58 gigatonnes higher by 2050, risking a temperature rise above 1.5 °C, with a 40% chance of exceeding 2 °C. Delayed grid development increases the risk of economically damaging outages.

Recommendations for Grid Investment:

³ <https://www.iea.org/reports/electricity-grids-and-secure-energy-transitions>

⁴

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1175649/electricity-networks-commissioner-letter-to-desnz-secretary.pdf

- Grid investment must nearly double by 2030 to over USD 600 billion annually to meet national climate targets.
- Emphasis on digitalising and modernising distribution grids.
- Grid plans should integrate inputs from long-term energy transition plans, enabling the growth of distributed resources and connecting resource-rich regions.

Barriers and Solutions:

- Barriers in jurisdictions like Europe, the United States, Chile, and Japan include public acceptance issues and regulatory reform.
- Solutions involve enhancing planning, allowing anticipatory investments, and streamlining administrative processes.
- Digitalisation and Skills: There is a need for skilled professionals and integrate digital skills into power industry curricula. Managing the impacts of energy transition and increased automation on workers through reskilling and on-the-job training is essential.
- Governments can support supply chain expansion by creating transparent project pipelines and standardising procurement and technical installations.
- Future flexibility is crucial, ensuring interoperability of system elements.

4 CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

To interact more deeply with the audience in the room and during individual interviews, the Mentimeter tool was used to gather insights about the main obstacles and facilitators for floating wind. The findings from this activity are displayed below.

4.1 Question-1: Types of organisations represented.

The participants' affiliations revealed a well-rounded representation across various categories, including institutions, universities, research centres, and industry players. Within other, key players such as the DNV-Certification and standardisation body, Net Zero Technology Centre, National Grid ESO, and ESC Power Systems Team were represented.

Figure 2: Type of organisations involved.

4.2 Question 2- Key Enabling Factors to prompt Investment.

As per the respondents, some of the crucial factors that will facilitate investment in floating offshore wind are a well-defined regulatory framework (which was four times more significant than other factors), the urgent need for grid investment, the growth potential of the local supply chain alongside technological maturity, and lastly, the availability of incentives. Notably, none of the participants chose "national transmission grid stability" or "significant market share and demand" as viable options.

Figure 3: Key enabling factors to prompt investment in floating offshore wind.

4.3 Question 3- Most significant risk in the Supply Chain

Concerning the risks associated with the supply chain, the most notable ones were identified as follows: the establishment of adequate infrastructure, the constraints in existing materials and resources competing with other more mature sectors, and the capability of the local supply chain.

Figure 4: Significant risks in Supply Chain for floating offshore wind

4.4 Question 4- Users of the sea and consideration in planning offshore wind's conscious and shared development?

Regarding the open question about the factors significant in the UK to promote the sustainable adoption of floating offshore wind while respecting other sea users and the stakeholders that should be considered in the strategic planning of offshore wind development, notable responses included local communities with existing maritime activities such as fishing, tourism, and shipping, as well as defence, oil and gas, island, and remote communities, among others.

In the strategic planning of offshore wind development, stakeholders such as local communities, fishing and tourism industries, environmental organisations, government bodies, energy companies, research institutions, and maritime transportation sectors should be considered. Engaging with these stakeholders ensures a comprehensive approach that addresses diverse interests and concerns, leading to a more sustainable and balanced offshore wind development strategy.

Crucial focus areas included incentives for local communities and advancing environmentally friendly technologies. The formulation of long-term strategies, enhancements to the regulatory framework, a re-evaluation of incentive policies for local communities and the entire transmission and distribution network, mindful alignment with the tourism-oriented nature of various maritime regions, and the advancement of technologies that not only reduce the environmental impact on the marine ecosystem but also positively influence the future energy system of the UK.

Figure 5: Sea Users to be considered in planning offshore wind's conscious and shared development.

4.5 Question 5- Ensuring active communities throughout the lifecycle of the project.

To ensure active community involvement throughout the lifecycle of floating offshore wind projects, participants highlighted areas of focus to promote community acceptance and support, leading to the successful implementation of offshore wind projects. The areas are highlighted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Suggested strategies to ensure active community involvement throughout the lifecycle

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The future of offshore wind is at a pivotal moment, where offshore wind is ready for rapid growth, with plans to support deployment to 2050 targets and beyond. However, the industry is dealing with a supply chain crunch, significant commodity price and interest rate inflation and a need for policy implementation in key areas.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
<p>Lack of Knowledge, Data, and Best Practice Sharing: Challenges arise due to insufficient sharing of lessons learned from consent procedures, technology testing, and data assessment across multiple sites, hindering progress in floating offshore wind projects.</p>	<p>Data and Knowledge Sharing from Consent to Operational Stages: Seamless data and knowledge sharing from consent stages to operational phases will facilitate smoother project execution, allowing for efficient problem-solving and innovation in floating offshore wind initiatives.</p>
<p>Grid Connection Readiness and Fit for Purpose: Critical challenges in grid connection, especially in the context of Holistic Network Design grid connections, create barriers for floating offshore wind projects. Extended waiting periods are deemed "unacceptable," impacting the development of low-carbon projects.</p>	<p>Addressing Grid Connection Challenges: Proactive efforts to address grid connection challenges, particularly in ensuring readiness and purposeful connections, serve as enablers for successfully implementing floating offshore wind projects.</p>
<p>Competitive Challenges: concerns about the competitiveness of floating offshore wind projects in the market, specifically regarding the ASP (Average Strike Price) in the CfD (Contract for Difference) mechanism</p>	<p>Continuous Innovation in Evolving Technologies: Emphasising continuous innovation and adapting evolving technologies and methodologies enables the industry to overcome challenges and drive progress in floating offshore wind projects.</p>
<p>Skill Shortages in STEM Fields: The industry faces barriers caused by skill shortages in STEM fields, which affect the development and implementation of floating offshore wind technologies.</p>	<p>Investment in STEM Education and R&D Funding: Investments in STEM education and funding initiatives, such as the Scottish Offshore Wind Energy Council (SOWEC), provide the necessary support to bridge skill gaps and fund crucial research and development, fostering advancements in floating offshore wind technology.</p>

<p>Market Factors: Fluctuations in commodity pricing and increased capital costs are impacting the industry, posing financial barriers</p>	<p>Learning from Real-World Project Examples: Drawing insights from specific projects like Northland Power in Canada and the Shetland offshore wind project, which navigate challenges related to oil and gas infrastructure, offers valuable lessons and solutions for overcoming barriers in floating offshore wind endeavours.</p> <p>Innovation and Collaboration: The industry is exploring innovative technologies like FLOW and tidal stream, focusing on research and development as enablers.</p> <p>Market Adaptation: The industry adapts to market dynamics by redirecting focus towards emerging markets, demonstrating flexibility as an enabler.</p> <p>Focus on Established Leases: A shift towards concentrating efforts on existing leases highlights a strategic approach, ensuring stable development and potentially serving as an enabler for the industry's growth.</p>
<p>Regulatory Uncertainty: The industry faces regulatory uncertainties, affecting the market's attractiveness for investors.</p>	<p>Policy Support: Tailored support measures can act as enablers, such as dedicating specific funding for floating offshore wind projects and considering technology maturity in ASP evaluations.</p>
<p>Environmental Impacts</p>	<p>Promoting co-existence with other sea-based activities Minimising the environmental impact on wildlife and having a net-positive impact on biodiversity</p>

Headlines Priorities:

Offshore wind energy is poised for rapid expansion. However, the industry contends with challenges such as supply chain constraints, soaring commodity prices, rising interest rates, and gaps in policy implementation in crucial sectors.

During our discussion with various stakeholders at the Floating Offshore Wind conference, it became evident that there is immense potential for the Scottish floating wind market, a sentiment echoed by many. Nevertheless, significant barriers must be overcome to tap into this potential, and time is of the essence. Key priorities are summarised in the table below:

SYSTEMATIC COORDINATION	POLICY & INVESTMENT CONFIDENCE	EFFICIENCY IMPROVEMENTS & INCREASED RELIABILITY	SUPPLY CHAIN & GRID REINFORCEMENT
<p>Coordinated manufacturing & supply chain management.</p> <p>A systematic approach for attracting investments, including addressing port infrastructure and grid reinforcement.</p>	<p>Clear, long-term government policies, especially concerning grid infrastructure and pricing.</p> <p>Providing investment confidence through transparent policies.</p>	<p>Advanced Design, Manufacturing and Assembly of Floating Substructures</p> <p>Securing adequate capacity and flexibility for energy integration</p>	<p>Clear government policies regarding grid, pricing, and distribution.</p> <p>Coordinated approach to the development of port infrastructure and network designs.</p>

Encouragingly, there is a united front comprising industry players, governments, and civil society, all dedicated to supporting the UK's journey toward a successful offshore wind future.

To address these challenges collectively, we can:

- Establish a seamless transition from project development to installation. Inject substantial volume into the market by providing certainty in the project pipelines and CR&D to support innovation.
- Design market strategies that align with the scale of the challenge, avoiding a race-to-the-bottom mentality.
- Enhance the regional and international supply chain through incentive-driven policies, strategic industrial approaches, and collaborative efforts.
- Prioritise the upgrade of national grids and ports infrastructure.
- Co-location of various seabed uses, such as energy production, CO₂ storage, ecosystem restoration, food production, tourism, recreation, and defence. Linked to abundant opportunities for innovation in exploring how different seabed uses can be combined. These opportunities exist on a multinational basis.
- Collaboration between the UK and the EU whilst specific decarbonisation plans are being developed. Effective development of energy basins is mutually beneficial. Collaboration is key to addressing concerns related to energy security and marine ecosystems across Europe.

- Transmission Grids highlighted as crucial enablers for the energy transition. The European Transmission System Operators (TSOs) are actively involved, as demonstrated by the Offshore Network Development Plans publication in January 2024.

6 APPENDIX- WORKSHOP AGENDA

FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND SIDE EVENT Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind

P&J Live, East Burn Road, Stoneywood Aberdeen, AB21 9FX

Location: **Conference Suite 4**, Floating Wind 2023, P&J Live, Aberdeen

Date & Time: 5th October 2023, 14:30-16:00

Organisers: Energy Systems Catapult, University of York, APRE

Agenda Items

14:630 – 14:45 Opening Remarks

Tim Stiven, Senior Development Manager (Marine) *The Crown Estate*.

Deborah Greaves, Director of *UK's SuperGEN Offshore Renewable Energy Hub* and Professor of Ocean Engineering, *Plymouth University*.

Riccardo Coletta, Project Coordinator MARINEWIND, *Agency for the Promotion of European Research, APRE*

***Moderator Dr Inès Tunga**, Practice Manager - Renewables, *Energy Systems Catapult*

14:45 – 15:30 Panel Session

Role of Network & Flexibility in Floating Offshore Wind, **Dr Corentin Jankowiak**, Network & Storage Systems Engineer, *Energy Systems Catapult*. Joined for the Q&A by **Francisco Correia da Fonseca**, Head of Engineering & Operations, *WavEC Offshore Renewables*

Co-location opportunities for sharing Infrastructure, Services and Supply Chain, **Tim Hurst**, Managing Director, *Wave Energy Scotland*

Competitive supply chain to support acceptance of floating wind, **Aldara Martinez**, Project Engineer, *SENER*. Joined for the Q&A by **Mary Harvey**, Senior Associate, *Carbon Trust*.

Licensing and Consenting Operational aspects, Kirsty Black/Debbie England *Scottish Government*. Joined for the Q&A by Anja Wittich, Environmental Marine Consultant, *SAMS Enterprise*.

UK Ports & Infrastructure to Unlock the Floating Wind Opportunity, **Marlene Mitchell**, Commercial Manager *Port of Aberdeen*. Joined for the Q&A by **David Willson**, Senior Project Manager (Ossian Project), *SSE Renewables*

Financing and Economic barriers, **Dr Paola Zerilli**, Scientific Coordinator Horizon Europe Commission, *University of York*.

15:30-15:45

Drawn conclusions and Next steps, **Dr Florence C Lee**, Renewables Systems Engineer, *Energy Systems Catapult*

